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Allin kausay virtue towards transcendence

Mayra Alejandra Castañeda Cataña ¹, María Isabel Pagani ², María Laura Vazquez ³, Mercedes Diemanz Hartz ⁴ and María Josefina Carlucci ^{1,*}

¹ Buenos Aires University. Institute of Biological Chemistry, Faculty of Exactas and Natural Sciences, (INQUIBICEN-CONICET), Virology Laboratory QB19. Buenos Aires, Argentina.

² National University of Lujan, Department of Social Sciences, Buenos Aires, Argentina.

³ Buenos Aires University. Faculty of Architecture, Design and Urban Planning (FADU). Image and Sound Design. Buenos Aires, Argentina.

⁴ Autonomous University of Barcelona. University School of Translators and Interpreters. Spain.

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Abstract

In the Andean-Amazonian Way of Life, Allin Kausay (Quechua language Allin stands for Magnificent, splendid and Kausay stands for life or existence). "Splendid existence" or "living well", it is an important principle of discipline that begins with Allin Ruay, doing things right, achieve them really, for this to happen it is necessary that each and every thing that arises must have a balance and should come in proportional pairs, which i show the natural order is understood in an indigenous society. Human beings by understanding the natural environment behavior propitiates the so called "h'ampi balance", art of knowing how to find the right balance between thoughts and feelings, where the criterion of "truth" (or Ch'ekka) full consciousness of the present, cause human presence means the living unity of all values. The purpose of these writings is to reconnect analogical links (between human-divine, mind- heart, meaning-form, matter- spirit, genetics- ethics, etc) for a new integrated human kind within its divine aspects (maximum consciousness of being) ancestral divine beings " virtue" aspects, therefore a substantial Union with Life, by all means what kind of values are there on metaphysical, social, cultural, or political ideas if the transcendent it is not found?

Keywords: Virtue; Consciousness; Philosophy; Creativity; Cosmos; Integration

1. Introduction

Jean Gebster interprets cultures development as the result of successive consciousness mutation of the consciousness structure [1]. He distinguishes a Pre logical stage before Greeks until Renaissance, logical stage starts from Renaissance and gives rise to a whole modern science then a third stage occurs in present times with a brand-new consciousness mutation and new thoughts, described by Munoz Soler as the analogical stage (analogy: relation of similarity between different things). Conscience thinks it is free but ignores the structures that precedes and determines it [2]. Language structure precedes it, others discourse precedes it, myth precedes it, institutional pacts precede it. Therefore, we can assert that consciousness is a socio- historical artifact that seeks some in order to be [3]. Prelogical conception tends to include humankind as part of nature and cosmos, individual consciousness dissolves within cosmic consciousness or identifies with nature as naturalistic pantheism or spiritualistic: God is everything. Logical conception arises with the reason awakening, Greeks vision, discovering opposites, spirit, matter, nature, history, knowledge of parts and concealment of whole, dialectics and contradiction. Irreducible dualism, atheism and dialectical materialism emerge as doctrines. The analogical conception discovers relations of similarity and harmony between spirit and matter, between being and the world between human and God [2]. Humans are neither equal to God nor opposed to God, but like God. Humans are not equal to each other, but alike. Humankind is determined from the origin to a transcendent end, but he

* Corresponding author: María Josefina Carlucci

is free to choose the path. Consciousness is essentially simple, but life is complex and contradictory, and between simple and complex, one and multiple, there are relations of analogy. A different ego is drawn between these anthropological structure - prelogical stage, the ego does not differentiate itself from the world, mystical participation, logical stage ego switches off from the surrounding world; and determines itself as subject in front of the object and in the analogical stage; ego no longer identifies itself nor separates itself from the world, but recognizes itself by reflection of similarity in the infinite cosmic consciousness. Prelogical structure made possible different types of wisdom such as Buddhism spiritual field, pre-Socratic philosophical field. Logical structure gave birth to science, technology and philosophical systems. Analogical structure is shaping a new science base on the analogical relationship genetics - ethics, logic - psychology, economics - spiritual, sociology - mysticism, virology - philosophy [4,5]. There is a change of how the forces play within the relationship between thoughts and feelings, will and consciousness, meaning and form. Martin Buber, *The Dialogical Principle* expresses, "The world generates in us a place to welcome it, it is not the world that settles in us, but it is the world that generates in us a place to welcome it" [6]. Successively, conditions will be installed in us to adjust or not to social- historical conditions configured in the world. There are perplexity moments, such as present times where we cannot give a straight answer, we do not have the capacity to deal with the stimulus that the world constantly show to us. Crisis invites us and give us an opportunity to create and ask ourselves lots of thoughts that we never had before. Must be taken into account that perception between being and things is not only and intellect activity, it is affected by feelings, emotions (form of love) when it is comprehended by the heart, secret link that brings separate worlds together, intellect understands the similarity of different forms understanding by analogy. The synthesis of elements is not realized by mysticism and ethics only, but also by physiology and chemistry.

Figure 1 Untitled series "Worlds", 2024

1.1. Reality, body and interpretation

Humans are connected to their community and the world by a continuous network of emotions. Andean cosmovision KAWSAY code expresses it this way "Vibration is everything, humankind must recognize himself as a part of earth and of its energy".

Recognition of existence, being a living thing and consciousness of the cosmos.

While its infinite diversity belongs to the heritage of species, impacted and affected by cultural and social events, within a particular context, which translates into physiological and psychological changes [7]. Emotions are often related to precise moral circumstances, it is not spontaneous but ritually organized and with meaning for others, encouraging vocabulary, speeches, gestures, facial expressions.....Emotion it is not a substance, not a fixed; cell that is found at the

same stage under the same circumstance of each human species, but though; it does extend throughout behavior, and does not cease to change constantly, every time relationships within the world are transformed, interlocutors change and each individual modifies the analysis of a situation. As confirmed by Candace Pert, emotions are electromagnetic signals that affect the chemistry, the electricity of every cell in the body and the world outside the body [8]. Affective life is imposed without any intention, it is not managed and sometimes goes against all will, even though it always responds to a cognitive activity linked to an interpretation of an individual of a situation in which it is immersed. They are imbued with meaning. An individual can be affected by relives threads of his memory impregnated with certain vision of the world and of others. There is no cognitive process without an emotional game being set in motion and vice versa. Emotions, writes James Averill... "Result from cognitive processes as complex as religion, art or science". We are not moved by the accidental release of a biological process, but by a specific commitment in a given situation that implies a recognizable physiological response as a consequence [9]. Likewise, the body like emotions are also a cultural construction. Individuals inhabit his or her body according to social and cultural orientations that interfere in their lives, representing them in their own way according to their temperament and personal history. In today's Western Societies, the individual is the body, appropriation of the body in an individual form allows creation of artifice thinking that it is independent of social life and has an existence in itself. Paradoxically and at the same time the body is erased from social symbolism and displaced to specialized fields such as medicine and physical education. However, it is a symbolic construction, not reality itself [10]. Andean cosmivision understood that physical body is represented by 70% water and 30% minerals, so solid matter is constantly changing and evolving. Nicolas Paucar says "In your body everything changes according to the experiences you have. Your physical body is affected by environment, such as you affect environment with your physical body. There is a large interconnection network that allows interaction with Earth and cosmos through the use of rituals, ceremonies, chants and plants. According to shamanism we are earth and water that walks with consciousness on this surface and water changes its molecular structure obeying intentions. Therefore 70% of our structure (water part) is possible to be completely restructured depending on interactions with the environment [11]. In summary, we can state that thoughts and emotions involve each other. According to Piaget, "there is no cognitive process without affective involvement and vice versa. Intelligence cannot be conceived without an affectivity that permeates it" [12]. Both are interrelated and are defined in a complementary manner. Society provides interpretation tools, there is no reality, there are interpretations. The construction of reality generates symbolic order that individuals internalize through education. This order shapes values, feelings, language, ways of moving, gestures, etc [13]. An emotion that is interpreted and acted in a certain way will give meaning to social life itself [14]. Searching for truth under these descriptions puts a limit to reality. It is indispensable as a true independent person to try to face reality as it is, not as we are told that it is or as we do like it to be.

1.2. Perception, Ego and Emotion

According to shamanic principles, the right body (left cerebral hemisphere) is dominated by the ego. This concept is explored in the works of Carlos Castaneda who describes the ego as a "foreign mind" [15]. When the ego assumes control over perception, it operates through a series of mechanisms: 1. A physical stimulus is generated, triggering a sensory experience. 2. The stimulus instantly elicits an emotional response. 3. The ego, with its pre-existing cognitive frameworks, distorts perception by assigning labels and meanings to the stimulus. 4. The ego then compares this manipulated information with reference memories, selecting meanings that align with its self-interest. This process involves drawing parallels with past experiences, leading to a positional response (for or against) to the current situation. The ego's influence can perpetuate pain or relaxation based on past experiences. By drawing from its stored knowledge, the ego reinforces mental schemes, recreating patterns that reaffirm memories. As noted by Lewkowicz consciousness perceives itself as free, yet it is preceded by structures that determine its responses [3]. This means that rational understanding on which *Homo sapiens* base their beliefs is far from impartial and is not objective, even if quality is pursued. The thoughts we create using this process often revolve around personal well-being and earthly interests, that is awesome. However, using our mind only for this purpose is a distortion of the original Character and a limitation of the capabilities of the mind. One of the most interesting functions that we tend to have forgotten is the management of information that our left side of the body provides (right brain hemisphere), which has the capacity to receive references and signals from subtle, immaterial or spiritual world. This type of knowledge manifests itself in the form of sudden intuitions, images or sounds that are later transformed into verbal thoughts. Once we have this information, we can apply it to concrete situations to achieve solutions [15]. Increasing knowledge allows us to use experience to relate facts and to obtain a complete picture of the situation, basically a global image. Andean Cosmivision refers to this principle, ANYA code which recognizes that each individual in his or her passage through life, gets impregnated with experiences that translates into belief systems and thought structures. This configures a point of view. The one who manages to understand and converge more points of view, is considered to have greater wisdom, the analogy is the view of a condor who can appreciate reality from height, having a wide and convergent perspective. An open trained mind allows you to stay awake in present time. Now is the only time when a person can act. The key for a person to develop and maintain physical and energetic abilities resides in the amount of energy available, knowledge gathered energy.

Hence, Knowledge is power. For example, a person may read a text and understand some of the information and then reread the same text with more energy and be able to extract subtleties that he or she could not before. The development and training of the mind goes hand in hand with saving energy in order to use our abilities to their full potential, and activities that lead to inner silence are very helpful but inevitably require discipline.

It involves ego judgements, such as observing and stopping, whenever we can, which requires sustained attention to present [16]. Martial arts provide this silence with their movements, conscious breathing, meditation, and often repetitive actions help to reach a state of suspension of thoughts to get in touch with our creative part.

Figure 2 Untitled series “Worlds”, 2024

1.3. Consciousness, rhythms and meanings

We are living a rupture process of forms and a new discovery of meanings. Frames that pretend to imprison life in are breaking down, penetrating life that enclosures sealed until yesterday and projecting new centers of equilibrium [17,18]. Herbert Marcuse has clearly pointed out that in order to develop new values, human beings indisputably need a new society. Marcuse says...“Real emancipation of men can take place in a different society only, and after a fundamental change of values, political, economic structures”...However further on he says...“at least some human beings with new values, aspirations must exist and perform their work before a massive change makes a general possible liberation” [19]. Resuming, to build a new society it is necessary to have a social model that is an individual that develops his possibilities as a human being, that provides indispensable brewed values to social masses to make the leap onto a higher level of consciousness. These two factors, social organization and individual consciousness, already exist in today’s world but they are insufficient for humanity to function as a planetary body. It is not about values or organization, but about energy and meaning. It is not enough to know the earth as matter, it is necessary to discover it as a living organism, to get in touch with the telluric forces of the planet and how can this telluric dimension of the human community can be conquered? Through human rooting on earth. Humanity will not be able to go too far into cosmic space, if it does not incorporate the invisible elements on earth. To conquer earth is a prior step to conquer space, and it is not enough to have advanced technology by the exploitation of natural resources, nor advanced sociology in the organization of human resources. What is needed today is not only a social organism in terms of politics and economics but a community in terms of human life, an essential and existential way of living that allows development of consciousness and makes possible the union between human beings without deteriorating their identity. The archetypal forms, which were formerly introduced as virtues, will now be activated as functions. What are theories worth? An important thing is to breathe not theories about gas exchange, and once you have learned to walk, what is

the point about movement theories? Likewise, only functions when it becomes reversible ensure the organic balance of life [2].

It is not only industrial problems that pollute the environment, also human products do.

Not only we do pollute outwardly, but we do pollute inwardly Our way of thinking, feeling and being are no longer enclosed in a subjective psychology but penetrate de circulatory stream of an ecological physiology (ocean- planetary) transformed into waves, of an ultra - physical, substance, unknown chemistry [20].

These new functions are revealed by means of a testimonial way, which is a method or the way that every living revelation has to manifest itself. A revelation that has been lived but not interpreted. Precisely testimony as a method of life as a way of being that today opens a; tremendous gap between those who see and those who interpret.

This New Age revelation encounters humanity as another universal good life such as sunlight, oxygen, intrinsic goods are given to us all "so they can live "Oxygen is oxygen to everyone. There is nothing to interpret here. Interpreted revelation has been the origin of division and war among human beings, but lived revelation is a bridge of reunion and participation. We must recover the space that is for human beings and the space we have lost. Once we have conquered the outer space, we have to return home, it is not a subjective inner space, but being space, and being space is the space of encounter through this space so men penetrates into the intimacy of the living cosmos. Space unites with consciousness in that subtle fabric of the universe.

The oscillation of consciousness in the inner space of being creates a new relationship with nature, actually in the ego world but do bond too with the below nature, its biological and psychic world, as though with the above nature supra cosmic world. In other words, a new relationship between cosmic life has arisen to be able to penetrate the cosmos, not only with knowledge and technique, but also with consciousness, which is not the same thing. The inner space is empty of things from the world, but it is not an empty space but the space of the being revelation. It is a sacred space where spiritual consciousness meets life. Spiritual values are substantially incorporated into the organism. The first function of the integrated man is a presence of action. Presence is a simple, specifically human act. It is the activity of a being in fullness of its consciousness and will. Why do we give to hierarchical first function presence? Because presence is a central function that combines by itself all of the being values. Presence means union, human being is determined from the beginning by union. The solar human is a more evolved being than the present one, a superior biological type with a new sensitivity and enough knowledge of;the laws of the universe and of life itself in a conscious and responsible way. Human presence cannot be characterized by a set of qualities, but by the force of its presence alone, it simply is and is worth what it is. It is the function of synthesis between spirit and matter, it is the fullness of being human in life and in love.

2. Ancestral legacy

2.1. Andean Cosmivision

Allin Kausay, "splendid existence" or "living well", is an important principle of Andean Amazonian discipline "way of life", which begins with Allin Ruay, "doing things well", and to do so it is necessary that each and everything arises from proportional pair balances, which i show the natural order is understood within the indigenous society.

A complementary proportional opposition or " Yanan - Tinkuy" between parities" example;heat - cold, light - dark, alkaline - acid, masculine - feminine, etc, is what produces "real existence" of things in motion, such as life, good weather, peace harmony, work etc, on the other hand, dis - proportion or imbalance of pairs can also arise and this means a deterioration of Allin Kausay which is why creates abnormal situations, such as diseases., storms, pain, unemployment etc everything that make us suffer. Human beings by understanding this behavior about natural environment, propitiates the so - called "hampi balance" which is the art of knowing how to find the "Meaning" according to moment and circumstance, within this complex game or plot of even forces that predetermine any situation of "Kausay" or "Exist".

It is worth knowing that within this "doing things well", the "middle ground";between the pairs of forces is not the same as the "right middle", within indigenous cultures, there must be a balance between quantitative criteria, but also qualitative, which is what differentiates indigenous logic from western ones, which is primarily quantative logic, which comes from its paradigm of origin in "unity" and not "parity" which is the indigenous paradigm [21]. Thus, criterion of truth is not given by idealistic dogmas as custom of the west is, but even less by simple practice, but by searching and finding the "H ampi balance. Nan;or;Path, or search for criterion of truth within indigenous culture of the Andes is

symbolized by a diagonal, in Simi or Quechua rune it is called “Ch ekkalluwa”, whose literal translation is “ Truth line “, that is why the “ Qhapaq Nan” or Path of the righteous, is built on a straight diagonal; which traces 45 degrees angle from the North -South axis and covers most of the hemisphere, on which on a straight line ancient and sacred temples were built such as the city of Tiwanaku as its center [22].

But the Allin Ruay, or “doing good” only covers one of the three “Pachas” Andean cosmovision, Kay Pacha “here and now” world. Kay Pacha is also a product of equilibrium of the fundamental pair or “Hanan Pacha -Uku Pacha” which are two worlds in successive and permanent contractive - expansive movement, a dynamic chat Mayans knew as the “Ollin State “. We will say that the “present” is the result between balance or “encounter” between “past” and “future” or what is almost the same between Hanan Pacha (cosmos future reality) and Uku Pacha (“underworld” past, ancestral, unborn) both identified with Allin Yachay principles of Allin Yachay or; “well thinking” and; “Allin Munay or “feeling well” respectively. Full balance for Allin Kausay is the result of the right balance between “Feelings and thoughts” where the criterion of “Truth (or Ch’ekka) becomes as full awareness of moment and circumstances of Allin Kausay or “splendid existence” as a great product of balanced or complementarily proportional thought and feeling. This is simple Andean cultura “Philosophy”, it is more difficult to practice, but no so hard when you learn it from a young age. Western culture has privileged “Thinking” since its origins in Ancient Greece, we continue to use “logos” and “epistheme”, reason and science as main weapons and virtues. But we have neglected a lot the emotional aspect, feelings and heart; “Allin Munay” serves that purpose, and Andean principle that indicates that in order to live splendidly, one must “Love well”, “Love strongly”, know how to feel cosmos, our community, our fellows human beings and surrounding environments, Mother nature, Pachamama. These principles “ Allin Munay” or “Loving well”, “feeling well”, “Allin Yachay” or “Well thinking”, “Knowing well” and finally “Allin Ruay” or “Doing well”, are the three pillar son which Allin Kausay or Sumac Kausay is built. This last one has an aesthetic connotation as “Sumac” is an adjective that qualifies as beautiful, lovely, but within indigenous cultures it often coincides with “ Allin”, “ Good”, “ Splendid”, “ Excellent”. Thus, ethical principles within the Andean order fully coincide with aesthetics. We must identify methods and paths for an individual “transitioning” alongside the system because if we do not change, the system never will. We must also try and start LIVING ,enjoying our existence, to do things like the Inkas used to , with “ Allin Ruway” for eternity, learn to find “ balance and equilibrium between pairs that creates existence, learn to walk Qhapaq Nan or “The righteous path” which is the “ Kay Pacha” between “Heaven and Hell” and this is the balance that is presented on the edge of the “union within diversity “ with cosmos, leaving behind bad habits of taking advantage through disintegration, separation, chronic fragmentation of “ Pairings” that make up our lives because “ being Human “ does not exist, what exist is TWO human beings (Human Pair) Males human beings and female human beings.

Understanding that this could be the beginning of practicing balance by trying to “ Think with your heart and feel with your head at once” until we can YLLANAY, a Quechua Word that means “ Ruminantion of the soul” or “feeling and thinking” within balance, understanding, accepting, recognizing and practicing “ testing” or “ balancing” the; “parity” of life or self;- healing “h ampi” given by interconnectedness or “ linkage” of the union of human pairs existence, among themselves and with cosmos, nature, beyond time , space, knowing how to use these “ good and bad” because these are never completely “dualized” or polarized. The elements from” the pair” always contain something “Good” and something “Bad” for life. What do exists are “parities in process of balance” within specific situations, each one in proportionally opposition according to a moment or circumstance. The transcendent solution lies in acknowledge how to balance or achieve a synergy resonance of “Good parts” while keeping “Bad parts” passive.

2.2. Maya Cosmovision Worldview

The ancient Mayan priests managed to adjust a terrestrial calendar to harmonious movement of the galaxy, so it will help them at all times to know past, present, future in a consistent way. It is where the prophetic gift is born, which is nothing more than a wise application of verifiable astronomical facts and how earth response to them.

The Mayans spoke to us about a rhythm of order that exists within the universe.

So, thanks to all this, they based their wisdom on the knowledge and mastery of time.

Life is really what you are able to make of it. Vast majority have become accustomed to watch and observe the passage of time without ever considering their active participation. The current period, Mayan priests called “Time of no time”, moment in which the great changes must occur to prepare sun and planets for a new era, moment in which human being, an expression of unique and evolved life, has the opportunity to continue on the path of deeping his existence and an opportunity to expand his state of consciousness [23]. Women were a fundamental pillar of human development on earth, as she took on the responsibility of seeking human harmony with nature and humanity. They practice cordiality and seek understanding. Dialogue and collaboration govern their relationships. Respect is undoubtedly an innate

quality for women. It belongs to their conscience and deepest feelings in their heart. A woman knows instinctively her vocation of unity and harmony among human beings of service and protection, her duty is to generate love without expecting anything in return. To make people acknowledge they must see that childhood is one of the paths that, with an open consciousness, we should take, collaborating in a necessary change. It must be clear that feminine and masculine are universal patterns of human psyche and are not restricted to a gender. Masculine and feminine simply belong to a structure of consciousness. If you ignore one of the two poles you are giving up many nuances and qualities of a human being. When feminine in its expression of love is activated, we immerse ourselves in the virtuality of love, beauty, passion, and spiritual renewal. Last era was conditioned by patriarchal societies. Feminine was not taken into consideration and social psychic structures become excessively mechanized, politicized and militarized. Judgement and rationality became dominant factors. Union is the key of the two decisive centers of our existence mind and heart, when they come together and walk aside everything is possible. Feminine conscious evolves through creative imagination relating to life and renewing energy. Expression of true love must meet a fundamental premise it must be completely selfless. This is observed in its pure form, in children's hearts, the love that they share with their mother and their closest environment.

It is pure, unconditional love, everything revolves around this extraordinary fact, human nature. Identification and respect for life like in Mayan culture. They promote that we all recognize each other as brothers, establishing a series of principles values, and attitudes that promote it.

Figure 3 Untitled series "Worlds", 2024

2.2.1. Inner knowledge

There is a first step for personal transformation that has always been taken into account in Mayan culture. There are three immaterial cosmic regions, governed by different types of energy, which are what make possible the different manifestations of our personality in the face of circumstances that surround us. These three cosmic regions or Mayan worlds are the celestial region, the earthly plane, and the one known as the underworld (Andean Trilogy). These three places are connected to each other and in order to make them understandable, we will represent them with the symbolic figure of a tree. The roots will sink into the lower space, the trunk would represent the earthly state, and the branches would penetrate the ethereal heights. This would be the great cosmic tree of the universe and its energies flow through it, exchanging and generating.

Going from one thing to another without anything stopping it, like when dead energy is able to transform into life or ascends to sublime heights. These blueprints energies also reside within the human psyche. The Earthly way would be the everyday aspect of our existence in our daily lives external circumstances, daily duties and relationship with other beings would shape your character and ultimately your personality. So, the cycle of life goes from earth to the underworld and from underworld to sky. Same path had to be traveled a human who longed for a transition to higher levels of consciousness. During his human existence, he has to first descend into his own underworld, where self- discovery takes place and goes through different tests in order to ascend with energy towards his own heaven. In your subconscious,

there also exists and underworld, the Realm of darkness and shadows, your personal underworld and its reality is imperceptible to senses. We are not mistaken human underworld is a place where death reigns (as an alchemical process required for a change of consciousness state) but also the keys of life and resurrection, passing from a state of equal life, of simple living beings to others where the sublimation of soul operates and causes the vital dimension of your existence to be redirected from that moment onto other paths in search of goals.

Here is the opportunity to penetrate that region of existence that probably remains closed and only each one of us can open it. We must not forget that within ourselves also exist all kinds of sublime potentialities that are based on overcoming trials from the depths of our psyche. The earthly world will never lead you directly to the light, needs to recognize your potential and decide to transmute that energetic and sublime light onto wisdom. Therefore, it is obvious that any variation within the earth's magnetic field, the planets gravity force, cosmic rays that daily penetrates the atmosphere and pass us through, must condition existence, modify it and even adjust it to newer energies of environment. Life is capable of constantly adapting to reality of the cosmos.

Therefore, energies that surround us are capable of causing involuntary changes in organic biochemistry and influencing our minds. So, magnetism exerts a very healthy influence on the human body organism, mind as it reactivates critical force. Disorientation appears when these fields are distorted. The biomagnetic relationship of a human being with circulating magnetic forces are signals detected by the subconscious. Therefore, a decrease in the intensity of the geomagnetic field will surely also diminish your psychic potential and consequently weaken the possibility of providing more transcendent meaning to your existence [24]. There is a clear call for human unity, in a meeting of mutual respect, harmony, tolerance and balance, enhancing innate qualities and virtues, since only here on earth, humans can be what they are and how they are, properly showing the so Little used of natural human values. This is what Mayans tell to their children. Take the child towards the cornfields and let them know that the cornfield ears would hear their thank you for the collective work of the earth, wind, water and sunlight, and that when you had eaten a bit of everything will enter you. Take him to the neighbor's son and tell him to be him, tell him to imagine that his hands are yours, eyes, and nose are also yours, the ask if you would ever be able to harm them. This is perhaps one of the most important teachings, putting your children in the place of others, trying to make them feel what your neighbor feels, by trying to understand what the other person feels and thinks life would be happier. The way to achieve it is easy if we apply common sense - observations of our actions. If we start observing our thoughts, feelings, desires, volitions...then will be able to see in others how they feel and think. Human brotherhood will be achieved when all individuals feel the way others can feel, mostly in different situations in life and of course, in daily relationships. Criticism and slanders would disappear. On the other hand, we must take into account the power of water as a giver of life and an unbeatable conductor of all kinds of vibrations. Water responds to emotional attitudes by applying a new attitude towards psychophysical health, accepting oneself as it is without comparing oneself to anyone, loving and being grateful towards oneself, so each action projects and reflects who we are. Fire is a living representation of knowledge. Light and warmth are identified with the sun that illuminates the soul of wise humans. The mystical inner fire is an extension of sacred and spiritual knowledge, which is why the being who has the ability to generate light is considered virtuous. Fire is capable of transforming matter and purifying by destroying material and negative elements. Its flames rise vertically towards the sky, seeking the divine origins of human beings. Likewise technological development of humanity has taken a significant leap in the a last two centuries, always based on a material extension of our body and our senses, without taking into account the possibility of developing other abilities that the human brain is capable of achieving.

This situation translates into a narrowness when it comes to expanding our thoughts, addressing transcendent issues, understanding human existence without the shackles of material. This behavior of technological civilization alienates and ultimately deprives us of inner peace. The consequence of all this is that the majority of humanity no longer perceives the very privilege of being human. Once the meaning of life is lost, the feeling of personal worth fades away. Life is no longer effective in itself; values are disappearing, and vices are replacing virtue. Global industrial civilization has a singular effect of blinding modern humans so they do not see reality of the sun as the creator of life and energy that must be taken into account in all our activities.

Figure 4 Untitled series “Worlds”, 2024

Nature has a sacred character for Mayan, since it is the most kind and extraordinary expression of Mother earth. Nature should be the protagonist during daily activities.

Participating in the collective consciousness that leads to integration with nature, out of respect for all living things and the sense of responsibility of humans as protectors of the environment are two fundamental values. In the same way, respect for human dignity is instilled, as we all have a mission to fulfill in life in harmony with the cosmos and above all with our fellow beings. The life cycle of an individual is not only about being born, growing, reproducing, dying. Mayans include transcending. Humanity, as the transcendental culmination of the expression of life, must stand as the guardian of nature and all its expressions of life.... starting with meditation and the activation of the power of the mind creating harmony of love, deep respect for others and each of the realities of our planet and spreading awareness to others. Human principles are universal, immutable, and transcendent because they identify with them and use them above all in their conduct. Values preserved with great care because they are considered guarantors of freedom and individual dignity, they are who will reconnect us with what we have lost planetary consciousness. Western culture has been built around deification of individuals ego and attached to any insignificant thing and the worst part is that when the mind feels attached to a thing, it becomes that thing, everything revolves around it. Materialism, possession, ambition a surrounding world trap towards obsession. This is not an external decision imposed on you, it is oneself who generates that need, who falls fascinated by possession. But when thoughts do not focus on objects, when you guide them towards your inner self, it is when you observe everything that you have in excess, it is then when you feel that the path will liberate you [23]. Gratitude and thankfulness are values that seem to have been banished from modern societies.

Mayans show gratitude not only for the favors received among humans, but also for everything that mother earth gives us, the dawn, a new day, stars at nightfall, rain, fire, land, food. Modern life isolates us from the relationship with the real world and cosmic rhythms and Project us into a agreed and illusory mental order. It is of great importance to be able to bring consciousness at will to reality that is not limited by time. Otherwise, there would not be a way to escape from the decay that time inevitably brings. Meditation can help, an active mind withdraws towards its source, and you experience a feeling of wholeness.

2.2.2. Harmonic Resonance

This concept has many applications within science and technology, but here we address transcendent harmonic resonance, which connects physical with ethereal and transcendental. In recent times technology revolution information has reached all of society. Information condensed in a binary system and stored on silicon memories.

But that information, in order to be truly beneficial, must fulfill a very simple premise, it must resonate, must become a flow of energy that passes from one to another.

Just like water in a bowl, it vibrates when we rhythmically strike it, and it is at that moment that real information is transmitted.

Resonance is simply to sound again, but not as an individual act, but as reflection of what has been received. Listening to voice and silence of what surrounds me is a form of perception that includes me as a vital element of a network.

Perceiving such network and acting in it allows us to interact within a living tissue that flows and continually modifies itself. It is entering into Resonance [25].

To resonate is to give and receive is reverberate. It is the clearest definition of communication as an exchange of information that, in the minds case and present moment, is truly precious. Therefore, the essence of information is not its content, it is resonance, and hence the importance of feeling things. When you feel resonance, you are assimilating an experience in a way that you can hardly know it only summarizing it in understanding its concept. Frequencies and tones, nuance information. In this sense, the energy that reaches the solar system, all its planets, and the sun is contributing towards the informational change in the most intimate part of existence. The cellular structure of our body is influenced by energy and seeks its balance in a harmonic resonance. This is the beginning of a new dimension within perception of reality, and the death of everything that cannot vibrate inharmony with a new way of conceiving existence.

3. The virtue of presence

The great consciousness of the Origin understands itself through and act of opening, splitting itself, to generate an initial movement with an evolutionary purpose.

This is an action of constant movement of division or separation, arising from the initial splitting, which leads to a permanent union of complementary opposites that tend to become Unity again. The same imprint of movement drives it to keep dividing.

This original scission give us the feeling that there is a reality, a life that happens outside of us. Until the intelligence of the Origin itself can consciously manifest its creative power, there is no possibility of generating an integrating movement, capable of unifying instead of dividing, capable to return to Origin.

Everything created and felt in one's own consciousness, permeating each realm, each species, each civilization, each system of thought and beliefs, is the narrative of creative unfolding the Original consciousness. In this sense, all reality is a symbol that we experience in a mythic way. Astrology, mythology, religion, and historical narrative is our way of expressing and bringing coherence to the perception of consciousness.

We are what every story creates and tells. As human presence, we are the living unit of everything. Without that presence there is nothing. To traverse the 32 paths of the Tree of Life implies to reach the maximum decoding and creative potential of our nervous system: our creative perception [16,18]. Each of these paths is, like nerves, a two-way street. The Word used in Sefer Yetsirah to name these paths is "Netivot", a very rarely used Word. Much more common is the Word "Derekk" which defines a public route, a rute used by everyone. "Nativ, on the other hand is a path opened by the individual for his own use. A hidden path, without milestones or signposts, that one has to discover by oneself

and find by own means. They are paths that must be opened by each individual [26]. It is also curious that 32 is Hebrew for lev and the same Word means heart.

There are as many ways to do this as there are embodied humans.

If we do it from the memory of what we have learned socially, morally and culturally, even from what we have learned academically, we will continue going around in circles, dividing, responding and decoding the past, on the basis of what has been established up until now. We will continue to believe that there is an inside and an outside belonging to two natures. Consciousness is one, expressing itself in myriads of singularities that can already be aware of its creative power, the basis of which is Love, the tangible certainty that one is all. If we begin to exercise presence connected to earth, to our bodies and pure sensations, open to receive frequency codes from the sky, we will begin to act from what is new, from action that happens in the present, integrating all the components of the moment in a way never seen before and unique. Creative presence is inspiration.

Figure 5 Untitled series “Worlds”, 2024

4. Conclusion

A different position in the scale of values and meaning of life emerges.

Somehow it has changed the ecological relationship between life and death, understood within the horizontal line of existence; appear to us as a beginning and an end.

But life and death understood a new parameter of meanings imply elevation or fall humanization or dehumanization. Restoring the original consciousness through virtues, the natural state of Being, is the only way humanity can transcend the level of Earth Human onto Solar human (Cosmic). Manifesting their virtues on earth but not expressing them. The energy of verbal communication is supportive, but not decisive. The key is the intention with which we act, aligned in coherence with our feelings and thoughts. To do so, you have to be strong of heart and not look back. The answer to this new call of feelings is to let them arise, to let them be, to be faithful to itself, to drown the love of the old human loved ones, which takes us back to the night of times.

The new humanity is not born under the sign of ideas, but under the sign of life, as announced and bequeathed by our ancestors. What does it mean? That it is not an ideal Union, but a substantial Union, new humanity is not committed to ideas, but to life.

Compliance with ethical standards

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References

- [1] Gebser J. 1972. The Foundations of the aperspective Word, Main Currents. Vol 29, 2
- [2] Muñoz Soler R, 1980. Synthetic anthropology. Signs, rhythms and functions of the planetary human. Editions Depalma. Buenos Aires.
- [3] Lewkowicz I. 2004. Thinking without a State. Subjectivity in the age of fluidity. Bs As. Ed Paidós.
- [4] Castañeda MA, Sepulveda CS, Carlucci MJ. 2021.The Omnipresent Power of the Invisible: from Viruses to Being Conscient World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 12(02), 518-525. Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2021.12.2.0617>;eISSN: 2581-9615
- [5] Castañeda MA, Amato R, Sepulveda CS, Carlucci MJ. 2022. The evolution of Knowledge: From Inert to Living Sciences. Global Journal Ecology 7(2): 082-089. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17352/gje.000066>. 2022.
- [6] Buber M. 2020. The Dialogical Principle. Hermida Editors S.L. España
- [7] Le Breton D.2012. Towards an anthropology of emotions. Latin American Journal of Studies on Bodies, Emotions and Society, N 10. Año 4. Argentina. pp69-79
- [8] Pert C, 2007. Everything You Need to Know to Feel Go (o)d. Edit: Hay House
- [9] Averill JR. 1980. Emotion and anxiety: sociocultural, biological, and psychological determinants, in: Rorty A.O. (ed.), Explaining emotions, Berkeley: University of California Press.
- [10] Fernández M. 2010. Affective culture and emotionality: emotions in social life. Latin American Journal of Studies on Bodies, Emotions and Society, Córdoba, N2, Año 2, p 84-86
- [11] Paucar Calcina N, 2014. This is how a Q'ero speaks. Editado por Hermanos Paucar. Cuzco. Perú.
- [12] Le Breton D. 1999. Ordinary passions. Anthropology of emotions. Buenos Aires: Editions Nueva Visión p108
- [13] Bateson G. 1986. La cérémonie du Naven, Paris: Biblio Essais.
- [14] Abelar T, 2018. Where wizards meet. Gaia Editions. Argentina
- [15] Castaneda C. 1998. The active side of infinity. Debolsillo, Penguin Random House Grupo Editorial. España

- [16] Vazquez ML, Castañeda Cataña MA, Diemanz Hartz M, Carlucci MJ. 2024. The meaning of “Being Art”: Perception and reality. World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 21(01),001-011. url:<https://doi.org/10.30574/wajrr.2024.21.1.2690>;
- [17] Castañeda MA, Sepulveda C, Carlucci MJ.2020. In Time of global planetary challenges: Metanoia. Austin Anthropol. 4(1): 1016. ISSN: 2768-0258
- [18] Diemanz Hartz M, Carlucci MJ. 2023. Sapere aude: Towards a brand new humanity. World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 18(01), 1128–1132. Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.1.0749>
- [19] Marcuse H, 1971. A Conversation with Herbert Marcuse. In Psychology Today 4:2, 35-40,60-66
- [20] Bateson G. 1976. Steps towards an ecology of the mind. Ed. Lohle Carlos, Buenos Aires. Argentina
- [21] Lajo J, 2016. To learn to live in the Sumaq Kawsay (V). America Latina en movimiento. ALAI. <https://www.alainet.org/es/articulo/179357>
- [22] Lajo J, 2005. “Qhapaq Ñan”, the Inca route of wisdom. Edit. Amaro Runa –CENES, Lima, Peru
- [23] Yaxal Balam, 2011. The Prophecy. Ed. Santillana Editions Generales, S.L
- [24] Firstenberg A. 2021. The Invisible rainbow: A history of electricity and life. Editions Atlantida. Capítulos 9,16. Girona. España
- [25] Vidoni, L 2019. Singing on the threshold. A cartography for collective singing and art.Ed Campo Grupal. Buenos Aires. Argentina.
- [26] Kaplan A. 1990. Sefer Yetsirah, the book of creation. Editorial Weiser Books.